

INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF FIBER METAL LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

In this research, different models were adapted and applied to determine the strain energy release rate of mode-I delamination in double cantilever beam specimens. Three models were considered: Euler-Bernoulli beam on Winkler foundation, Timoshenko beam on Winkler foundation and Timoshenko beam resting on two-parametric elastic foundation. The effective flexural modulus in those models was determined with two different methodologies, plane stress resultant method and plies arrangement method. An experimental investigation was performed to determine interlaminar fracture toughness on fiber metal laminates made of multidirectional and plain weave carbon epoxy composite without and with alternating aluminum alloy 2024-T3 layers. Comparison of the analytical and experimental results is made in order to determine the model which better describes the behavior of the fiber metal laminate. The described models provide explicit closed-form solutions for compliance and strain energy release rate. It was noted that compliance of multidirectional composites is higher than that of plain weave composites. In addition, it was observed that the addition of the metallic layers increased the energy absorption capability of the composite material under mode-I delamination for multidirectional composites; the highest increment on fracture toughness was observed in fiber metal laminates made by multidirectional composite compared with that using woven prepreg.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber metal laminates (FMLs) are hybrid composites consisting of alternating layers of thin metallic sheets and carbon fiber reinforced epoxy prepregs. FMLs are materials promising better mechanical and damage tolerance properties than the individual constituents. FMLs have been developed primarily for aircraft structures as a substitute to high strength aluminum alloys. FMLs are being used in many secondary structural applications in airframes. Because of their lower density and superior performance in fatigue and damage tolerance, they are also being considered for use as a primary structural material for several aircrafts [1].

The advantages of FMLs have been clearly identified since the beginning of their development [2]. Advantages of these materials include superior fatigue performance (FMLs have slower crack growth rate than monolithic aluminum), high strength (bearing strength in fasteners joints), impact resistance (the damage tolerance is better compared with composite components) and flame resistance. These improvements offer weight and maintenance reduction that is reflected in operating costs savings.

The most commonly used metal for FML is aluminum. The FML with glass fibers (trade name GLARE), and Kevlar fibers (trade name ARALL) have been evaluated for many potential applications in aircraft structures [3, 4]. More recently, GLARE has been selected for the upper fuselage skin

structure of Airbus A380. Nevertheless there is a great interest in the use of other metallic materials as the titanium alloys due to its high specific mechanical properties and corrosion resistance [5-9].

The lack of reinforcement in the thickness direction of the laminated composite is likely to de-bond layers. Delamination reduces mechanical properties and limits the safe life of a composite component. Interlaminar fracture toughness is an important parameter in the design of safe composite structures. One typical approach is using the double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen for determining critical strain energy release rate or toughness, G_C , under mode-I and mode-II delamination mode. The DCB test geometry, test procedure and analysis for fracture toughness evaluation are limited to thin and unidirectional fiber composites. The standard analysis methodology may not be properly accounted for angle-ply laminates or FMLs. Delamination of angle-ply has a feature of a crack between dissimilar anisotropic materials which substantially complicates the fracture mechanics.

The aim of this paper is to investigate the feasibility of applying different DCB models to predict interlaminar toughness of composite laminates and FMLs. Four models were considered: the compliance calibration method (CCM), Euler-Bernoulli beam on Winkler elastic foundation (EB-WEF), Timoshenko beam on Winkler elastic foundation (TB-WEF) and Timoshenko beam resting on two-parametric elastic foundation (TB-PEF). The effective flexural modulus in those models was determined with two different methodologies. An experimental investigation was performed to determine interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates and FMLs made of multidirectional and plain weave carbon epoxy composite with alternating aluminum alloy 2024-T3 layers. Comparison of the analytical and experimental results is made in order to determine the model which better describes the behavior of the laminates.

2 ANALYSIS OF DCB SPECIMEN

DCB specimen, Figure 1, is extensively used for determining critical strain energy release rate G_{IC} under mode I delamination, and has been accepted as an ASTM standard (D5528) for mode I delamination fracture characterization of unidirectional composites under limited conditions. On a deeper analysis of the DCB specimen, the two arms of the specimen rotate slightly due to the elastic support provided at the crack tip. The elastic foundation model is illustrated in Figure 2. The cracked region is considered as a free beam of length a , loaded with a concentrated load P at one end. The uncracked section beyond the crack tip is modeled as a beam on an elastic foundation.

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of the DCB

2.1 Effective moduli of a laminated beam

The important parameters in the estimation of strain energy release rate of angle-ply laminated beams are the effective flexural modulus, E_{fx} , and the effective out-of-plane extensional modulus, E_z . Different methodologies have been described in the literature to evaluate the stiffness of laminated composite beams under bending [10]. In this work we use two approaches for E_{fx} : the approach called plies arrangement [11]

$$E_{fx} = \frac{12\bar{D}}{h^3} \quad (1)$$

where

$$\bar{D} = \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \frac{1}{\bar{S}_{11}} z^2 dz = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{1}{[\bar{S}_{11}]^k} (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \quad (2)$$

and the approach named plane stress-resultant method

$$E_{fx} = \frac{12}{d_{11} h^3} \quad (3)$$

where

$$[d] = ([D] - [B][A]^{-1}[B])^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where [A], [B] and [C] are the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrices, respectively.

The out-of-plane extensional modulus, E_z , is estimated according to the method proposed in [11]

$$E_z = \frac{\sigma_z}{\varepsilon_z^0} = \frac{t}{\sum_{k=1}^N (1/[\bar{C}_{33}]_k) [1 - [\bar{C}_{13}]_{k, A_{xz}} - [\bar{C}_{23}]_{k, A_{yz}}] t_k} \quad (5)$$

where t is the full laminate thickness, t_k , is the ply thickness, N is the total number of plies in the laminate, and \bar{C}_{ij} are the transformed stiffness of each ply which are defined in [11].

2.2 Compliance calibration method (CCM)

According to ASTM D5528 [12] we generate a least square plot of $\log(\delta/P_i)$ versus $\log(a_i)$; the slope of the best-square fit n is determined. Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness is determined with the following equation

$$G_I = \frac{nP\delta}{2ba} \quad (6)$$

Another approach included in [12] is the modified beam theory method (MBT) which is given by

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2ba} \quad (7)$$

where P is the load, δ is the load point displacement, b is the specimen width and a is the delamination length.

2.3 Euler-Bernoulli beam theory on Winkler elastic foundation (EB-WEF)

Assuming the length of the un-delaminated region much larger than beam thickness the following expression is proposed in [11]

$$G_I = \frac{12P^2 a^2}{E_{fx} b^2 h^3} \left[1 + 1.28 \left(\frac{h}{a} \right) \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_z} \right)^{1/4} + 0.41 \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)^2 \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{E_z} \right)^{1/2} \right] \quad (8)$$

2.4 Timoshenko beam theory on Winkler elastic foundation (TB-WEF)

The Timoshenko beam theory on Winkler elastic foundation model was developed in [13] to predict the compliance and G_I for unidirectional DCB specimens. The following expression was presented in terms of effective properties on laminated composites

$$G_I = \frac{12P^2 a^2}{E_{fx} b^2 h^3} \left[1 + \sqrt{\left(\frac{E_{fx}}{6E_z} \right)^{1/2} + \frac{1}{12} \frac{E_{fx}}{kG_{xz}} \left(\frac{h}{a} \right)} \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

2.5 Timoshenko beam theory on two-parametric elastic foundation (TB-PEF)

A simple closed form relation for compliance and G were developed in [14] considering the Timoshenko beam theory and two-parametric elastic foundation as a generalized case.

$$G_I = \frac{12P^2 a^2}{E_{fx} b^2 h^3} \left[1 + 2 \sqrt{\frac{E_{fx}}{9E_z} + \frac{E_{fx}}{18kG_{xz}} + \frac{kG_{xz}}{6E_z} \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2} + \left(\frac{E_{fx}}{12kG_{xz}} + \sqrt{\frac{E_{fx}}{9E_z}} \right) \left(\frac{h}{a}\right)^2 \right] \quad (10)$$

Figure 2. DCB on elastic foundation

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Materials and specimen preparation

Four kinds of samples were considered: multidirectional $[(0, 90)_3]_s$ samples without aluminum layers hereafter called just **MD-composite**, plain weave composites samples without aluminum layers hereafter named just **PW-composite**, FML samples made by multidirectional carbon composite prepregs and thin 2024-T3 aluminum layers identified as **MD-FML** and FML samples made by plain weave carbon composite prepregs and thin 2024-T3 aluminum layers called just **PW-FML**.

The fabric used in the multidirectional composites (MD-composite) was unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg DA409UG35 (0.195 mm thickness). Each specimen consisted of 12 plies (giving a plate thickness of 2.35 mm) with a sequence of orientation $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$. The fabric used in the woven composite samples (PW-composite) was carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg DA4518 plain weave (0.22 mm thickness); each specimen consisted of 12 plies (giving a plate thickness of 3.05 mm) with a sequence of orientation $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ]_s$, where 0° corresponds to the warp direction of the prepreg.

Fiber Metal Laminates consisted in intercalating prepreg plies and aluminum alloy 2024-T3 bare sheets with thickness of 0.3 mm (before surface treatment) without adding any adhesive film. The stacking sequence in MD-FML was $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/Al/0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ (giving a plate thickness of 2.57 mm) where the rolling direction of the aluminum coincides with 0° of prepreg. The stacking sequence in PW-FML was $[0^\circ/0^\circ/0^\circ/Al/0^\circ/0^\circ]_s$ (giving a plate thickness of 2.9 mm) where the rolling direction of the aluminum coincides with the warp direction of prepreg.

The stacking sequence chosen for FML was arbitrary; the purpose is just to evaluate the influence of adding the aluminum layer and compare the behavior of the FML with that of the woven and multidirectional composite samples. Prior to the stacking step on the FML manufacturing, the aluminum sheets were subjected to a mechanical-chemical treatment to increase the adhesion between the metallic sheet and the composite ply. The procedure consisted first in a manual abrasion with sandpaper followed by immersing the sheets in a sulfuric acid/ferric sulfate etch solution, see [15]. Autoclave processing cured all the specimens.

The geometry of the specimens are shown in Figure 1 according to ASTM D 5528; main dimensions are $a_0 \approx 38$ mm, $L=125$ mm, $b=25$ mm. A thin Teflon film was inserted at the mid-plane of

the panels during lay-up process to define a starter delamination crack. Figure 3 presents a cross section of the woven composite (a) and FML (b). The elastic properties of carbon epoxy composites and aluminum alloy bare sheet are summarized in Table 1, these properties were determined experimentally. For the woven composite, the subscript 1 refers to longitudinal (warp) direction and the subscript 2 refers to transverse (fill) direction.

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of, (a) PW-composite, (b) PW-FML

Table 1. Elastic properties of the different materials used

	PW	UD	Aluminum
E_{11} (GPa)	49.81	81.81	66.9
E_{22} (GPa)	53.34	5.76	
G_{12} (GPa)	3.51	2.72	25.7
ν_{12}	.048	0.28	0.3

3.2 Fracture testing

Before fracture testing the specimen edges were painted to facilitate the crack tip localization and crack length measurements. A MTS testing machine was used under displacement control. A plot of the load (P) versus displacement (δ) was generated for each test.

Each specimen was loaded at a constant displacement rate of 1mm/min until the crack propagated between 5 and 10 mm. the cross-head was stopped. After the crack growth arrested completely, the crack length was measured. The crack extension process was then repeated in about 10mm increments until final crack length reached approximately 80mm. this procedure gives fracture toughness values for each specimen and compliance measurements for each crack length.

Compliance of DCB specimen was measured at various discrete crack lengths. The experimental values of C and a were fitted to a power function to obtain the parameters R and n in the next expression

$$C = Ra^n \quad (11)$$

The energy release rate, G , is obtained by differentiation of equation (11) with respect to crack length. G_c is obtained by substitution of the measured critical load P_c at the onset of crack advance into the expression

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P_c^2 n R a^{n-1}}{2b} \quad (12)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 shows a typical load-displacement diagram where the crack advance steps are clearly identified. Compliance of the DCB specimen was evaluated from experimental load-displacement data at various crack lengths. Figure 5 presents a typical experimental compliance curve, in this case for the MD-composite DCB specimen. The dotted line represents the power function best fit. According to equation (11) the parameters R and n may be determined from this fitting process. Using these parameters, the strain energy release rate can be evaluated from equation (12).

Figure 4. Load displacement curve, MD composite

Fracture toughness values evaluated with the critical load at the onset of crack advances according with equation (12) are shown in Figure 6 for the MD-composite case. Estimations of initiation fracture toughness using the different models described previously, equations (6) to (10), are also plotted for comparison. Note that CCM value of G_{IC} , given by equation (6) is in good agreement with the experimental result.

The DCM arms, opened during the test, are shown in Figure 7; this case corresponds to the MD-composite sample. Note the crack fracture path follows a slightly undulated trajectory, due to the 90° plies failure.

Figure 5. Compliance calibration curve, MD composite

Figure 6. Fracture resistance curve, MD composite

Figure 7. Interlaminar fracture test of a DCB specimen

Figure 8. DCB specimens under loading, approximately crack length is $a=45$ mm, (a) MD-composite 1, (b) MD-FML 2, (c) PW-composite 2, (d) PW-FML 1

Figure 9. Fracture surfaces of the DCB specimens. (a) MD-composite, (b) PW-composite, (c) MD-FML, (d) PW-FML.

Table 2 gives out-of-plane modulus, E_z , determined by equation (5), and effective flexural modulus, E_{fx} , calculated by equations (1) and (3), for the different DCB used in this study. Table 3 summarizes the interlaminar fracture toughness values obtained experimentally through equation (12) and those values predicted by the different models explained previously with equations (6) to (10). Note that in all the cases the analytical models overestimate the fracture toughness. It is worth noting that compliance of MD samples is higher than that of PW specimens, this fact is verified in Figure 8 where DCB samples approximately with the same crack length are shown and it is appreciated that displacement for PW specimens is greater.

Table 2. Dimensions of the DCB specimens. Flexural modulus and out-of-plane extension modulus

	configuration	b (mm)	2h (mm)	E_z (GPa)	$E_{fx}^{(1)}$ (GPa)	$E_{fx}^{(2)}$ (GPa)
MD-composite	[0/90/0/90/0/90] _s	25	2.35	6.07	43.75	41.16
PW-composite	[0/0/0/0/0/0] _s	25	3.05	6.24	49.81	49.81
MD-FML	[0/90/0/AI/0/90] _s	25	2.57	6.09	44.88	44.01
PW-FML	[0/0/0/AI/0/0] _s	25	2.90	6.25	50.12	50.17

⁽¹⁾Plies arrangement method

⁽²⁾Plane stress – resultant method

Table 3. Predicted and experimental fracture toughness values

	G_{IC} Experim init (J/m ²)	G_{IC} CCM (J/m ²)	G_{IC} EB-WEF (J/m ²)	G_{IC} TB- WEF (J/m ²)	G_{IC} TB-PEF (J/m ²)
MD-composite	798.6	835.0	1184.2	1229.0	1211.1
PW-composite	869.0	909.3	1317.4	1371.5	1384.2
MD-FML	1066.5	964.6	1529.8	1590.6	1566.6
PW-FML	220.5	218.1	475.9	496.5	487.6

5 CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of applying different DCB models to predict interlaminar toughness of composite laminates and FMLs was investigated. Four models were considered: the compliance calibration method (CCM), Euler-Bernoulli beam on Winkler elastic foundation (EB-WEF), Timoshenko beam on Winkler elastic foundation (TB-WEF) and Timoshenko beam resting on two-parametric elastic foundation (TB-PEF). An experimental investigation was performed to determine interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates and FMLs made of multidirectional and plain weave carbon epoxy composite with alternating aluminum alloy 2024-T3 layers.

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